

THE SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF REINFORCEMENT IN PM Al/SiC_p MMCs AND ITS EFFECT ON THEIR PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Whilst thorough mixing between the two components of a powder metallurgical route MMC can be achieved, a "necklace" structure can be observed in hot isostatically pressed materials which leads to small scale inhomogeneities in the finally worked composites. The origins and effects of these inhomogeneities have been investigated for a number of Al-4wt%Cu - 20wt%SiC_p MMCs. It was found that as the matrix:reinforcement particle size ratio approached unity, the spatial distributions became more uniform, and a greater reduction in thickness could be achieved during hot rolling before edge cracking initiated.

Keywords: MMC, homogeneity, spatial distribution, powder metallurgy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced metal matrix composites produced via a liquid route often exhibit inhomogeneous distributions of the reinforcement due to the mixing characteristics of the process, settling of the reinforcement, or the clustering of particles due to the growth of matrix dendrites into the remaining liquid during solidification [1]. The powder metallurgical (PM) route was introduced as a means of reducing the problems of wetting and interface reactions encountered in liquid route processing. An added benefit of the PM route is that the spatial distributions of the reinforcement are also improved although agglomeration still occurs on a smaller scale.

Many properties of MMCs have been found to vary significantly with the volume fraction of reinforcement. These include physical properties [2], recrystallisation and texture [3], fracture [4], tensile properties [2], wear [5], and precipitation behaviour [6]. This paper reports results of a research program on the optimisation of microstructures in PM route MMCs. The origins of inhomogeneous distributions of reinforcement in particulate reinforced PM route MMCs will be discussed together with the effects these have on the behaviour of the material during processing and on its mechanical properties. Theoretical approaches and practical techniques for the quantification of spatial distributions are discussed elsewhere [7].

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Ingots of Al-4wt%Cu alloy were prepared by induction melting high purity aluminium and copper under inert conditions and were remelted in the melting chamber of a high pressure gas atomiser in an Ar atmosphere prior to atomisation with helium or nitrogen as the atomising gases. The atomisation pressures were 2.1MPa and 3.4MPa for the coarse grade and finer grade of powder, and the metal to gas mass flux ratio was 2.

MMCs were produced by mixing matrix powder of 40 μ m mass median diameter with 3 μ m and 17 μ m SiC_p, matrix powder of 50 μ m with 3 μ m and 17 μ m SiC_p, and matrix powder of 80 μ m with 29 μ m SiC_p. Thus the matrix:SiC particle size ratios were 2.35, 2.75, 2.94, 13.33 and 16.67. In all cases the matrix powder was not separated by sieving or gas classification. The production route for all MMCs was as follows : (i) Baking of the SiC_p for 1h at 200°C and screening, to deagglomerate the reinforcement, (ii) Blending of matrix powder with 20wt% SiC_p mixtures in a Turbula T2C blender for 1h, (iii) Cold compaction of the blended material in aluminium cans of 57mm internal diameter to a maximum load of 100kN, (iv) Vacuum degassing for 4h to 6h, (v) Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIPping) for 90min at 530°C and 2450MPa pressure, followed by slow cooling, (vi) Scalping of the cans to get cylindrical billets of 45mm diameter and 70mm height. (vii) Hot forging at 475°C to a thickness of 33mm, and then to 22mm after a reheat of 20min. Preheating to 475°C was for 1h. (viii) Hot rolling to 2mm thickness in fifteen passes, at 475°C, with several minutes reheat between passes. Preheating to 475°C was for 1h.

Microstructural characterisation of the materials, at both the HIPped and rolled conditions, was done with reflected light microscopy. Specimens were mounted in conductive bakelite, ground and diamond polished to 1 μ m using standard metallographic techniques, and finished with "OPS" KOH suspension. Tensile testing was carried out on the rolled composites in the as-rolled condition and after solution treatment at 530°C followed by cold water quenching. Since this study was aiming to establish the effect of reinforcement segregation on the processing characteristics and the mechanical properties of the composites the above heat treatment was chosen in order to restrict the influence of matrix precipitates on the mechanical properties of the materials. Tensile testing was done at room temperature on an Instron 1175 static testing machine with a 100kN load cell and at a cross-head speed of 1mm/min.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical microstructures of three rolled MMCs, with varying matrix:SiC particle size ratio, are shown in Figure 1. The composite with the large particle size ratio (Figure 1a) exhibited segregation of the reinforcement, whereas the structures of the two composites with smaller particle size ratios were more homogeneous (Figures 1b, c). Microscopy revealed that these microstructures were directly related to their respective structures in the HIPped condition, see figure 2, where the microstructure was "necklaced", as the large matrix particles were surrounded by the smaller SiC particles. At high matrix:SiC particle size ratios the structure was highly necklaced (Figure 2a), and when the size ratio became closer to unity the extent of necklacing was much less (Figures 2b, c). It is difficult to compare the latter two microstructures because they have similar particle size ratios but different sizes of SiC_p. This raises the question of whether it is correct to compare the microstructures at the same magnification, since for a constant volume fraction the interparticle spacing between the reinforcing particles will rise approximately linearly with increasing particle size [8]. The microstructures in Figure 2 are reproduced in Figure 3 so that the SiC particles appear to be of the same size in each material (and therefore would appear to have the same mean interparticle spacing). Figure 3 gives a better comparison of the spatial distribution of SiC

particles in each material.

A first consideration in determining the origins of the necklace structure is the conversion of volume fraction of reinforcement V_f to number fraction N_f of reinforcing particles. Assuming that the particles of each component (i.e., matrix, SiC) are mono-sized and that they are all perfectly spherical

$$N_f = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{1}{V_f} - 1\right) \left(\frac{D_{SiC}}{D_{mat}}\right)^3} \quad (1)$$

where D_{mat} and D_{SiC} are the particle diameters of the matrix and SiC_p respectively. For a constant volume fraction, the number fraction of SiC particles increases with increasing matrix:SiC particle size ratio. Number fractions of SiC particles estimated from eq.(1) for the materials of this study, are given in Table 1. The MMCs with large particle size ratios have number fractions of SiC particles extremely close to one indicating that the structure must be made up of a small number of large matrix particles, with a very large number of small SiC particles between them, hence the highly necklaced structure.

The HIPped microstructures can also be explained in terms of the packing of rigid spheres. Consider three packings of matrix rigid spheres; primitive cubic, face centred cubic and close packed hexagonal. For each packing we can calculate the unit cell volume, V_{Cell} , in terms of the radius of the matrix spheres, R_{mat} ; the volume fraction of the unit cell which is solid, S ; and a critical ratio of occupation, C , the latter being the ratio of the diameters of the matrix spheres to a smaller (reinforcement) sphere which can just fit into the interstices between the matrix spheres [9]. If the matrix:SiC particle size ratio is below C then the packing of the matrix spheres will be disturbed and ideal packing will break down. If the matrix:SiC particle size ratio is greater than $2C$ then two reinforcing spheres can fit into each interstice and we can say that a cluster has formed. We can also calculate from eq.(2) the maximum volume fraction, V_f^{max} , of reinforcing spheres which can be contained in each packing without either disturbing the matrix spheres or being clustered

$$V_f^{max} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{R_{mat}}{C}\right)^3}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{R_{mat}}{C}\right)^3 + V_{Cell}S} \quad (2).$$

The spatial properties of the three packings, and their associated maximum reinforcing sphere volume fractions, minimum possible matrix:reinforcement sphere size ratio, and maximum size ratio to prevent clustering, are given in Table 2. The data reveals that of the three ideal packings considered only the primitive cubic could be achieved for the materials of the present study ($V_f=0.186$). However clustering in the primitive cubic case would begin at a matrix:SiC particle size ratio of 2.73 and so the MMCs with size ratios of 13.33 and 16.67 would be expected to be highly clustered. This was confirmed by the composites shown in figures 2 and 3 and all other MMCs which exhibited some clustering of the SiC since their particle size ratios straddle the particle size ratio for the onset of clustering.

The tensile properties of the MMCs are given in Table 3, together with results of the

unreinforced alloy (80 μm mass median powder particle size) which was processed in exactly the same way. In both the as-rolled and solution treated conditions, the 0.2%PS and UTS increased with the addition of the reinforcement and the strain to failure was reduced. There was no correlation between matrix:SiC particle size ratio and these properties. The over-riding influence on these properties was only the absolute particle size of the reinforcement. There was no correlation between the strain to failure and either the particle size ratio or the absolute size of the reinforcement alone. Therefore it is concluded that the inhomogeneities in the distribution of the reinforcement were of too small a scale to affect the tensile properties of the MMCs.

Whilst the spatial distribution of SiC_p was of little consequence to the tensile properties of the MMCs it became apparent that the matrix:SiC particle size ratio had a significant influence on the processing of the materials. All MMCs behaved similarly during processing up to and including the forging stage, without the introduction of any visible defects. However during rolling the materials began to crack at the edges. The reduction in thickness achieved before edge cracking began varied from material to material. Figure 4 shows the reduction in thickness achieved for each material as a function of the matrix:SiC particle size ratio. An approximately linear trend showed that greater reductions in thickness could be achieved in materials with small particle size ratios, but cracking could not be prevented completely. Not only did materials with large particle size ratios crack at an earlier stage of rolling reduction, but the intensity of the cracking was also more severe, see figure 5. The importance of SiC_p clusters on edge cracking during rolling became more evident with microscopical examination. Figure 6 is an optical micrograph of an edge crack in a MMC reinforced with 3 μm SiC_p. Several important features should be noticed in figure 6. First, whilst the major part of the crack is perpendicular to the edge of the rolled sheet, the tip of the crack has turned into a region rich in SiC_p parallel to the edge of the sheet. Branches of the crack are very short and blunt, but appear only in regions rich in SiC_p. In similar regions a short distance from the surface of the crack, large pores have initiated and grown, probably due to lack of plastically deformable matrix. It is likely that coalescence of these pores is the mechanism for this extensive edge cracking. The influence of homogeneity of the microstructure on edge cracking during rolling suggests that it could affect the fracture properties of the material in service.

The tensile properties of the MMCs have shown that of the different reinforcements sizes the smallest (3 μm) is the most advantageous to the strength of the composites even though the reinforcement is highly segregated. This segregation is detrimental to the processing of the material in terms of the extent of edge cracking during hot rolling, increased material wastage and adds to the overall fabrication costs. One could go some way towards predicting the extent of reinforcement segregation either from the number fraction of particles or from the packing of rigid spheres. The former indicates that a matrix powder size below 9 μm would be required in order to achieve spatial distributions of reinforcement closer to those of the MMCs containing the larger SiC_p sizes (in other words in order to achieve a more uniform composite structure). The latter indicates that some form of unclustered packing of the matrix powder and SiC particles could only be achieved with a matrix:SiC particle size ratio below 2.73, i.e. a matrix powder size below 8.2 μm would be required for the 3 μm size SiC_p. Aluminium alloy powders at these fine sizes cannot be produced easily, either by gas atomisation using argon or nitrogen as the atomising gases or by other processes. Separation of the fine end of particle size distributions of batches of powder by sieving or gas classification could give the required size of matrix powder but at very considerable cost, increased safety penalties and would result in large quantities of surplus over-sized powder.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The spatial distribution of SiC_p in PM route MMCs is a function of the matrix: SiC particle size ratio. As this ratio increases the structure of the MMCs in the HIPped condition becomes more "necklaced", and the distribution of SiC_p in the rolled materials becomes more segregated. The extent to which the HIPped structure is necklaced has been explained in terms of the number fraction of SiC_p as a function of particle size ratio, and in terms of the ability to produce ideal packings of rigid spheres during processing.

The segregation of the reinforcement is of a scale which does not affect the tensile properties of the materials. It is the size of SiC_p which has the major influence over strength.

The presence of the reinforcement causes edge cracking to occur during the rolling of PM route Al-4wt%Cu/20wt% SiC_p MMCs. The edge cracking occurs at an earlier stage and is more severe when the matrix: SiC particle size ratio is high.

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Table 1. Estimated number fraction of SiC particles of MMCs of different matrix:SiC particle size ratios.

Matrix:SiC _p Size Ratio	Number Fraction (N _r)
40:17 (2.35)	0.748
80:29 (2.75)	0.826
50:17 (2.94)	0.853
40:3 (13.33)	0.998
50:3 (16.67)	0.999

Table 2. Packing data and calculated parameters for ideal packing of two rigid spherical components.

Packing	V _{cell}	S	C	V _r ^{max}	Minimum Size Ratio	Ratio for Onset of Clustering
Primitive	8R _{mat} ³	0.5236	1.366	0.282	1.366	2.732
FCC	4√2R _{mat} ³	0.7405	2.415	0.066	2.415	4.83
CPH	4√2R _{mat} ³	0.7405	4.44	0.011	4.44	8.88

Table 3. Tensile properties of reinforced and unreinforced Al-4wt% Cu

Treatment	Matrix:SiC _p	σ _{0.2%} (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	ε _r (%)
	Size Ratio			
As Rolled	40:17 (2.35)	171	269	6.6
	80:29 (2.75)	157	236	6.9
	50:17 (2.94)	190	276	7.5
	40:3 (13.33)	177	302	7.4
	50:3 (16.67)	205	321	6.6
	80:-	110	196	16.3
Solution Treated 1 Hour at 530°C	40:17 (2.35)	157	304	12.3
	80:29 (2.75)	152	276	10.2
	50:17 (2.94)	150	293	11.0
	40:3 (13.33)	174	379	14.0
	50:3 (16.67)	174	369	10.3
	80:-	97	248	26.4

Figure 1. Optical micrographs of rolled MMCs of different matrix:SiC particle size ratio, (a) 40:3 (13.33), (b) 50:17 (2.94), (c) 80:29 (2.75). - 50µm.

Figure 2. Optical micrographs of the MMCs in Figure 1, but in the HIPped condition. - 200µm.

Figure 3. As Figure 2, but at different magnifications, to take in to account the variation of interparticle spacing with reinforcement particle size.

Figure 4. Variation of reduction in thickness prior to edge crack initiation during hot rolling with the matrix:SiC particle size ratio.

Figure 5. Rolled sheets of MMCs of different matrix:SiC particle size ratio, highlighting the intensity of edge cracking, (a) 50:3 (16.67), (b) 40:3 (13.33), (c) 40:17 (2.35).

Figure 6. Optical micrograph of a region close to the edge of a rolled sheet of a 3μm SiC_p reinforced MMC.